

RULE OF LAW IN OUR CONTEMPORARY SOCIETY

¹Mr. Nitya Nand Pandey, ²Dr. Govind Singh Rajpal

¹Assistant Professor, ²Assistant Professor

^{1,2}Amity Law School

^{1,2}Amity University Rajasthan, Jaipur, India

Abstract : Inevitably, a developed system of administrative law emerged in England and need to control the arbitrary action masquerading in the garb of discretion arose.¹ The Committee on Tribunal and Enquiries known as Franks Committee. came out with recommendation to control effectively administrative action. And this continues to be human endeavor in our contemporary society.

INTRODUCTION

Rule of law is intimately connected with human dignity and liberty.

Plato's formulation of law in his work, *The Republic*, shows the importance of rule of law. In his *Republic*, Plato asserted that if philosophers were kings or kings philosophers, government by will would be intrinsically superior to government by law. Experience eventually taught him that ideal was not attainable and that if ordinary men were allowed to rule by will alone, the interests of the community would be sacrificed to those of the ruler. Accordingly, in *The Laws* he modified his position and urged the acceptance of the "second best", namely, government under law.

RULE OF LAW IN OUR CONTEMPORARY SOCIETY

Since then the question of the relative merits of rule by law as against rule by will has been often debated. In the aggregate the decision has been in favour of rule of law. On occasions, however, we have slipped back into government by will only to return again, sadder and wiser men to Plato's "second best" when the hard facts of human nature demonstrated the essential egotism of men and the truth of the dictum that all power corrupts and absolute power corrupts absolutely. Bracton's dicta that if the King has no bridle one ought to be put upon him, and that although the King is under no man he is under God and the law. In the words of Khanna, rule of law is now the accepted norm of all civilized societies. Even if there have been deviations from the rule of law, such deviations have been covert and disguised for no government in a civilized country is prepared to accept the ignominy of governing without the rule of law. Admittedly its content is different in different countries; nor is it to be secured exclusively through the ordinary courts. But everywhere it is identified with the liberty of the individual. It seeks to maintain a balance between the opposing notions of individual liberty and public order. In every State the problem arises of reconciling human rights with the requirements of public interest. Such harmonizing can only be attained by the existence of independent court which can hold the balance between citizen and 'State and compel governments to conform to the law.'²

A state of negation of rule of law would not cease to be such a state because of the fact that such a state of negation of rule of law has been brought about by a statute. Government under the rule of law demands proper legal limits on the exercise of power. This does not mean merely that acts of authority must be justified by law, for if the law is wide enough it can justify a dictatorship based on the tyrannical but perfectly legal principle *quad princip placuit legis habi vigorem*. The rule of law requires something more. Powers must first be approved by Parliament, and must then be granted by Parliament within definable limits. Dicey's concept of rule of law has been criticised by writers since it equates the rule of law with the absence not only of arbitrary but even of wide discretionary powers :

There are, I believe, ideas of universal validity reflected in Dicey's three meanings of the rule of law... (1) in a decent society it is unthinkable that government, or any officer of government, possesses arbitrary power over the person or the interests of the individual; (2) all members of society, private persons and governmental official alike, must be equally responsible before the law; and (3) effective judicial remedies are more important than abstract constitutional declarations in securing the rights of the individual against encroachment by the State.³

¹ *Breen v. Amalgamated Engineering Union*, (1971) 2 & B 175 per Lord Deming} M.R.

² *A.D.M., labalpur v. S.Shukla*, AIR 1976 SC at 1254

³ See Friedman : *LAW IN CHANGING SOCIETY* (2nd ed.) 501.

The rule of law is not a vague or nebulous concept. In the Words of Khanna, "whatever might be the position in peripheral cases, there are certain aspects which constitute the very essence of the rule of law. Absence of arbitrariness and the need of the authority of law for official acts affecting prejudicially rights of individuals is one of those aspects. The power of the courts to grant relief against arbitrariness or absence of authority of law in the matter of the liberty of the subject may not well be taken to be a normal feature of the rule of law."⁴

In the words of Hoodherti, the essence of rule of law is that public officers are governed by law, which limits their powers. It means government under law, the supremacy of law over the Government, as distinct from government by law not merely supremacy of law, which will apply to totalitarian States also, the rule of law is used in contradistinction to "rule of man" and "rule according to law".⁵ All modern States totalitarian or otherwise are States according to law but this does not imply that rule of law prevails there. Rule of law is thus something superior, something ideal, an admixture of jus and lax. In that sense it is akin to natural law.

In *Keshvanand Bharti v. State of Kerala*,⁶ the Supreme Court held that rule of law was part of basic structure of the Indian Constitution. This has found manifestation in subsequent decisions.

In *Indira Nehru Gandhi v. Raj Narayan*,⁷ holding Article 329A (4) as unconstitutional (under this provision, the election of the Prime Minister and Speaker could not be challenged in a court of law) the judges said that it was violative of rule of law which was the basis of structure of the constitution. All the judges were of the view that the 39th Amendment was violative of rule of law. Ray, C.J., observed that since validation of the election of the Prime Minister was not under any law, it was violative of the basic postulate of rule of law. Similarly, Mathew, J., was of the view that clause (4) of Article 329A offended the rule of law which was the pervading law of the constitution. The rule of law excludes arbitrary action in any sphere of the government. Beg, J., observed that jurisdiction of the court could not be taken away without causing injury to the basic postulates of rule of law and justice within the politically democratic constitutional structure.⁸ In *Delhi Transport Corporation v. D.T.C. Mazdoor Congress*,⁹ Ramaswamy, J., succinctly formulated the meaning of rule of law thus : The absence of arbitrary power is the first essential of rule of law upon which our whole constitutional system is based. In a system governed by rule of law, discretion when conferred upon executive authority must be confined within defined limits. The rule of law from this point of view means that decisions should be made by the application of known principles and rules and, in general, such decisions should be predictable and the citizen should know where he is. If a decision is taken without any principle or without any rule, it is unpredictable and such a decision is the antithesis of a decision taken in accordance with the rule of law. justice should not only be done but it must also be seen to be done.¹⁰

Reference may also be made to the International Commission of justices and their Delhi Declaration of 1959 which was confirmed at Lagos in 1961. The Commission has divided itself into the following committees. Committed on individual liberty and Rule of law; Committee on government and rule of law; Committee on criminal Administration and Rule of law; and Committee on judicial process and Rule of law, In the 1957 Chicago Conference the principles of Rule of law that emerged are the following :

(1) The Rule of Law is an expression of an endeavour to give reality to something which is not readily expressible; this difficulty is primarily due to identification of the rule of the 'law with the concept of rights of man-all countries of the West recognize that the rule of law has a positive content, though that content is different in different countries; it is real and must be secured principally, but not exclusively, by the ordinary courts.

(2) The Rule of Law is based upon the liberty of the individual and has as its object the harmonizing of the opposing notions of individual liberty and public order. The notion of justice maintains a balance between these notions. Justice has a variable content and cannot be strictly defined, but at a given time and place there is an appropriate standard by which the balance between private interest and the common good can be maintained.

(3) There is an important difference between the concept of Rule of Law as the supremacy of law over the government and the concept of rule of law as the supremacy of law in society generally. The first concept is the only feature common to the West connoting as it does the protection of the individual against arbitrary

⁴ A.D.M., Jabalpur v. S. Shukla, AIR 1976 SC at 1263.

⁵ Hoodherti : CONSTITUTION AND ADMINISTRATIVE LAW (3rd ed.) 42.

⁶ AIR 1973 SC 1461.

⁷ AIR 1975 SC 2299.

⁸ See also *P. Sambamurthy v. State of A.P.*, (1987) 1 SCC 362 : *Miss Veena Seth v. State of Bihar*, AIR 1983 SC 339.

⁹ AIR 1991 SC 101.

¹⁰ PK. Ghosh, *I.A.S. v. LG. anput*, (1996) (1) scr 751 (SC)

government-different techniques can be adopted to achieve the same end and the Rule of Law must not be conceived of as being linked to any particular technique. But it is fundamental that there must exist some technique for forcing the government to submit to the law; if such a technique doesn't exist, the government itself becomes the means whereby the law is achieved. This is the antithesis of the Rule of Law.

(4) Although much emphasis is placed upon the supremacy of the legislature in some countries of the West, the Rule of Law does not depend upon contemporary positive law, it may be expressed in the language of positive law but essentially it consists of values and not institution; it connotes a climate legality and legal order in which the nations of the West live and in which they wish to continue to live.

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH AND
ANALYTICAL REVIEWS (IJRAR) | E-ISSN 2348-1269, P- ISSN 2349-5138**
An International Open Access Journal

The Board of
International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews (IJRAR)

Is hereby awarding this certificate to

Nitya Nand Pandey

In recognition of the publication of the paper entitled

RULE OF LAW IN OUR CONTEMPORARY SOCIETY

Published In IJAR (www.ijrar.org) ISSN UGC Approved & 5.75 Impact Factor

Volume 6 Issue 1 March 2019

PAPER ID : IJAR19J2961

Registration ID : 198769

R.B. Joshi
EDITOR IN CHIEF

UGC and ISSN Approved - International Peer Reviewed Journal, Refereed Journal, Indexed Journal, Impact Factor: 5.75 Google Scholar

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH AND ANALYTICAL REVIEWS | IJAR

An International Open Access Journal | Approved by ISSN and UGC

Website: www.ijrar.org | Email id: editor@ijrar.org | ESTD: 2014